

Overall study design

Title of the study	Plasma and Platelet Lipidome Changes in Fabry Disease		
Document creation date	06/13/2024	Corresponding Email	lsibjb@nus.edu.sg
Principle investigator	Bo Burla / Singapore Lipidomics Incubator	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Institution	National University of Singapore	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	1-phase system	1-phase system	Butanol/Methanol (1/1)
pH adjustment	None	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Ion source	ESI
Separation type 1	LC	MS Level	MS2
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP for all panels, except SPBPs and Ga2/LacCer where HILIC was used	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.7
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
MS type	QQQ	Resolution at MS2	Low
MS vendor	Agilent	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Injection blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool, Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	No	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification data, Identification data, Quantification and identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	10.5281/zenodo.11634068	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	Analysis of SPBPs was done after TMS-derivatization of lipid extracts.

Sample Descriptions

Plasma from Healthy Controls and Fabry Disease patients / Human / Plasma

Provided information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	24
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	120	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	120	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Platelets from Healthy Controls and Fabry Disease patients / Human / Cells

Provided information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	24
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Freeze-thaw cycles	0
Instant sample preparation	No	Additives	None
Time to freeze (min)	120	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Plasma from Healthy Controls and Fabry Disease patients / Human / Serum

Provided information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	24
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	120	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	120	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier (precursor with water loss) with qualifier transitions (precursor without water loss) checked

1) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cer 18:1;O2/16:0[D31]	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)	Cer XX:1;O2/XX:X	
Cer 18:1;O2/16:0[D31]	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)	Cer XX:2;O2/XX:X	
Cer 18:0;O2/8:0	LCB 18:0;O2(-HO)	Cer XX:0;O2/XX:X	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Response of the ceramide internal standard (Cer 18:1;O2/16:0[D31]) was lower than expected, we therefore corrected the concentration based on re-calibration with the NIST SRM1950 plasma and internal reference values for Cer 18:1;O2/16:0 in this matrix
Type I isotope correction	No		

2) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)			
LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)			
LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

2) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
HexCer 18:1;O2/8:0 LCB	18:1;O2(-H3O2)	HexCer XX:X;O2/XX:X	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

3) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)			
LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

3) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

4) Hex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex3Cer	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)		
	Hex3Cer(-Hex3)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked
Which assumptions were presumed?	<p>Measured Hex3Cer species are Gb3 (globotriaosylceramides), as in the literature (at least the major form of) Hex3Cer reported in human plasma and cells are thought to be Gb3. Did not find any information about Hex3Cer isobars other than Gb3 (except of maybe of iGb3, which however is present at trace amounts compared to Gb3 in human)</p>		

4) Hex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

5) GB4[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	GB4	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
	Fragment name		
	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)		
	Hex3Cer(-Hex3)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

5) GB4[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

6) GM3[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	GM3	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
	Fragment name		
	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

6) GM3[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

7) SPB[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SPB	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name SPB(60)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

7) SPB[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

8) SPBP[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SPBP	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name SPBP(60)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

8) SPBP[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	Measured in HILIC

9) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
	Fragment name		
	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
	SM(184)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Co-elution of quantifier with qualifier transitions checked

9) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

10) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
	Fragment name		
	LPC(184)		
	LPC(104)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

10) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

11) LPC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC O	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name LPC O(104)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

11) LPC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

12) LPC P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC P	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name LPC P(104)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

12) LPC P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

13) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name LPE(-141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

13) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

14) LPE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE P	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name LPE P(-141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

14) LPE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

15) LPI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name LPI(-277)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

15) LPI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

16) LPS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name LPS(-185)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

16) LPS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

17) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	PC(184)		
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups. PC 28:0 was classified to contain PC 14:0_14:0, PC 36:6 (peak b) to contain PC 14:0_22:6, and PC 38:5 (peak group b) to contain PC 16:0_22:5 based on an external measurment using same chromatography of NIST plasma in negative mode
Which assumptions were presumed?	PC 28:0 was classified to contain PC 14:0_14:0, PC 36:6 (peak b) to contain PC 14:0_22:6, and PC 38:5 (peak group b) to contain PC 16:0_22:5 based on an external measurement of NIST plasma in negative mode		

17) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	Fully saturated PCs isotope-corrected for isobaric SM M+3 signals

18) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name PC O(184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

18) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

19) PC P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC P	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name PC P(184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

19) PC P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

20) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	PE(-141)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

20) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

21) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	PE O(-141)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

21) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

22) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
	Fragment name		
	FA+C2H5N		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

22) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

23) PI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
	Fragment name		
	PI(-277)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

23) PI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

24) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	PS(-185)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

24) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

25) FA[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	CAR(85)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

25) FA[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

26) CE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name CE(369)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

26) CE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

27) DG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name -FA(+OH)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

27) DG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

28) TG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	-FA(+OH)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	a, b, c at the end of lipid names indicate different peak (isomer) groups

28) TG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

29) LSM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LSM	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name	LSM(184)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

29) LSM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

30) LHex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LHex3Cer	Limit of detection	S/N ratio			
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes			
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No			
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No			
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-			
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Agilent MassHunter Quant			
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
Fragment name						
LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)						
LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)						
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-			
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No			
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes			
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-			
Check isomer overlap	Yes					

30) LHex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio						
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Agilent MassHunter Quant						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>N-glycinated Lyso-Gb3</td> <td>LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	N-glycinated Lyso-Gb3	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
N-glycinated Lyso-Gb3	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)								
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	No								

31) LHex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LHex2Cer	Limit of detection	S/N ratio			
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes			
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No			
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No			
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-			
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Agilent MassHunter Quant			
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
Fragment name						
LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)						
LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)						
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	-			
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes			
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes			
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-			
Check isomer overlap	Yes					

31) LHex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio						
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Agilent MassHunter Quant						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>N-glycinated Lyso-Gb3</td> <td>LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	N-glycinated Lyso-Gb3	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
N-glycinated Lyso-Gb3	LCB 18:1;O2(-HO)								
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	No								

32) Ga₂[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Ga ₂	Limit of detection	S/N ratio			
MS Level for identification	MS ₂	RT verified by standard	Yes			
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes			
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes			
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-			
Fragments for identification	Lipid Identification Software	Agilent MassHunter Quant				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>LCB 18:1;O₂(-HO)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LCB 18:1;O₂(-H₃O₂)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	LCB 18:1;O ₂ (-HO)	LCB 18:1;O ₂ (-H ₃ O ₂)		
Fragment name						
LCB 18:1;O ₂ (-HO)						
LCB 18:1;O ₂ (-H ₃ O ₂)						
Isotope correction at MS ₂	No	Data manipulation	-			
MS ₂ verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No			
Background check at MS ₂	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes			
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-			
Check isomer overlap	Yes					

32) Ga₂[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio						
MS Level for quantification	MS ₂	Normalization to reference	No						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ₂	Lipid Quantification Software	Agilent MassHunter Quant							
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Hex2Cer 18:1;O₂/16:0[D₃]</td> <td>LCB 18:1;O₂(-H₃O₂)</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	Hex2Cer 18:1;O ₂ /16:0[D ₃]	LCB 18:1;O ₂ (-H ₃ O ₂)			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
Hex2Cer 18:1;O ₂ /16:0[D ₃]	LCB 18:1;O ₂ (-H ₃ O ₂)								
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	No								